

METHODS AND FORMS OF EDUCATION IN MODERN PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *This study presents information on the formation of a method of education using modern pedagogical methods in education, mainly using modern pedagogical theories of education. Also, the collaborative form of education based on innovative education based on modern educational programs is currently giving good results. There is an opportunity to improve the quality of education through the use of new pedagogical methods and new educational theories in the education system. Theoretical information on the use of pedagogical methods based on modern innovative educational programs is presented.*

Keywords: *Modern education, pedagogical methods, educational methods, educational program, collaborative learning, innovative pedagogy.*

Introduction

In today's era of globalization, the socio-economic development of society, technological advancement, and the expansion of information flows require new approaches to the education system. The concept of innovative pedagogy occupies a central place in the educational process and is of great importance in the formation of modern teaching technologies, new theoretical concepts, and creative teaching methods. Innovative pedagogy is a scientific and practical direction aimed at introducing innovations in pedagogical activity, effectively organizing the teaching process, and developing the intellectual, creative, and spiritual potential of the individual.

This approach is primarily associated with building a new foundation for the interaction between the teacher and the student, focusing education on the individual, encouraging independent thinking, and using the capabilities of digital technologies.

Innovative pedagogy involves a radical renewal not only of teaching methods, but also of the entire education system, increasing the professional competence of the teacher, and harmonizing curricula with the requirements of the times. Therefore, this study focuses on the essence of innovative pedagogy, the main theories of educational methods, the importance of innovative approaches in the educational process and their practical application. The educational outcome of the student's individual work in the formation of his own knowledge is supported by the activities of the group and the team.

The student shares resources with the group, uses group work for learning. The structure of the activity is flexible and open, and a collaborative situation such as search is further formed.

Noyabr, 2025-Yil

The teacher plays the role of a facilitator in learning, and the group acts as a source of information, motivation, a means of self-help and mutual assistance, and a special place of interaction for the construction of collective knowledge. In cooperative learning, there is no a priori distribution of roles, as in simple joint (cooperative) work. Individuals gradually merge into a group that has become a whole and whose potential is greater than the sum of its parts, which often allows for high-quality work. At the same time, there is both individual responsibility for the common work and the responsibility of the entire team. All members of the group are in close and constant contact, each brings their own collaborative efforts to the group, each can contribute to the work of other members of the group to increase productivity, and thus join the principle of continuous improvement of each of their performance. Collaborative development is carried out within the task and the project as a whole.

The interaction of group members is long-term, and coordination of the team in achieving the final goal helps. For greater coordination between group members, the number of its participants should not exceed five people. Often, when older students, and sometimes teachers, hear the term collaborative learning, it automatically associates it with a negative context of working in groups, which is likely to cause problems in the school environment. Collaborative learning-based methods and mechanisms make them want to abandon the concept of collaboration (old methods), which they see as unrealistic or as an attempt to shift the learning burden from the teacher to the students. In open distance learning, we must reiterate the benefits of collaborative work and the need to support each of its participants, especially in terms of motivational dynamics, where the external aspect is necessary for success.

This first concern of some students is noteworthy, as it is an example of a misunderstanding of what has become an absolutely integral approach to the greatest viability of teaching and learning in digital networks based on multi-vector learning. The following principles can be used to select and gradually implement collaborative mechanisms of learning, as well as collaborative (collaborative) learning: The results of students' joint activities lead to mutual understanding, which, perhaps, allows for a more effective educational process than independent work; Oral and written communication of students helps to achieve the best understanding; The collaborative learning program further develops students' ability to understand the relationship between social interaction and mutual understanding through lived experience; The lesson should clearly and predictably determine the state of understanding of information, some elements of deep understanding of the subject; We are putting forward the ideas that participation in games based on new innovative ideas in the development of cooperation skills should be voluntary and free, but at the same time strongly supported.

It is clear that the cooperative learning mode requires a wider participation of stakeholders.

The ability of the group to develop this human capital is perceived by some as a sign of collective intelligence. According to Pierre Levy, collective intelligence is intelligence distributed throughout the world, because no one knows everything, but everyone knows something. Knowledge is present in man, and not in some transcendent being that organizes its wider distribution in society; therefore, a well-organized team is recognized as a key human asset, personally coordinated in real time.

In the field of pedagogy, the mechanism for organizing multi-vector educational models is similar to the methods of cooperative learning and collaborative teaching, which are focused on the importance of interaction between members of a small group - students.

The purpose of cooperative (group) forms of learning is to move from simple learning actions to a group form of organizing learning. As for the definition of the concepts of “teaching with pedagogical methods in improving cooperative skills” and “cooperative teaching based on multi-vector approaches”, there are definitions that emphasize their difference and definitions that are consistent with the concept of “cooperative teaching based on multi-vector directions”. It is advisable to combine the intellectual efforts of students in groups of 4 or more people to search for explanations, solutions, and create a teaching methodology. In this article, the term “cooperative learning” is used in its unifying meaning. The cooperative process should have the following characteristics. First, it can be achieved through the correct use of methods in the direction of thought pedagogy. The lack of instructions and structures in the methods can lead to difficulties in achieving learning goals. High-quality education is ensured by setting clear learning goals. The second characteristic of cooperative learning is the continuity of cooperation.

In cooperative learning activities, all group members must work together to achieve the goals. That is, if one group member does all the work, it is not cooperative learning. Regardless of whether all group members are given the same task or whether participants work together on different tasks that make up one large project, all students must complete the learning task together.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that, taking into account the results of innovative pedagogy implemented through teaching techniques, the assimilation of new knowledge by students during the lesson should be meaningful, which contributes to the formation of a deep understanding of the subject, the ability to find connections between objects and phenomena, as well as the ability to associate new information with existing knowledge.

Thus, cooperative learning is one of the most convenient and effective ways to ensure the activity of two or more groups of students working together and evenly distributing the workload according to the intended learning outcomes. In addition to social and psychological aspects, two factors related to the cognitive sphere can contribute to the effectiveness of cooperative learning - the choice of a well-thought-out task and the use of methodologies that help increase the level of mental effort necessary for learning activities.

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Noyabr, 2025-Yil

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Noyabr, 2025-Yil

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